

EXPLORING THE TWILIGHT ZONE: THE LIVED EXPERIENCES OF NIGHT-SHIFT WORKERS IN CALAMBA LAGUNA

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15255558>

ABSTRACT

Night shift work is part of the essentials of several industries, such as health, protection services, food delivery, and entertainment. Flexibility and good money may be its attractions, but it does have its consequences on the circadian rhythm of the body, and sleep and mental well-being may be compromised in various ways. This phenomenological study investigates the lived experiences of night shift workers in understanding the impacts of night shifts on sleep, mental health, and quality of life. Key findings include the fact that many respondents appreciate the opportunity to balance work and family responsibilities and seek supplementary economic opportunities by working night shifts. The challenges include social isolation, sleep deprivation, and workplace fatigue. All these challenges are mitigated by workplace support such as flexible scheduling, health and wellness programs, and adequate financial compensation, thus improving job satisfaction and retention. Recommendations included hiring adjustments, rest facilities on duty, and incentives so that work environment may change and improve.

Keywords: *Night shift work, employee well-being, work-life balance, sustainable working conditions*

INTRODUCTION

In the current world, with increasing competences of companies; many companies are often located in different time zones thereby requiring shift work during the night. They become commonplace across various sectors within the society; some of the essential sectors include food preparation and delivery, entertainment, protection services, medical care, and transport among others (Cannizzaro, 2020).

Julnes and Angel (2022) mentioned that working at night to maintain regular operations is still possible and required in today's environment and culture, but it offers advantages as well as disadvantages for employees. It can, in turn, allow for greater flexibility and often higher pay than usual; nevertheless, shifts that are considered irregular might cause the body to adjust itself to interrupt its circadian cycle, resulting in a variety of difficulties. To further understand this unusual work and organizational lifestyle, a deep exploration should be done, focusing on the lived experiences of night shift workers.

Understanding the lived experiences of night shift workers is important for increasing their quality of life while also guaranteeing their health and safety. This paper explored the relatively unexplored world of the night workforce, talking about the problems and benefits that face individuals who work during peaceful hours. The phenomenological method used in this research gives considerable insights to politicians, employers, and healthcare practitioners. It can be used to establish methods to improve the well-being of night shift workers and build a more sustainable work environment.

Research Questions

Central Question

The aim of this phenomenological study is to understand the impact of night shift work on sleep and mental well-being on casino employees. This undertaking was covering the actual experiences and reasons of the chosen individuals.

Corollary Questions

1. How do night shift workers describe their personal experience during working?
2. What are the emerging themes based on the gathered data?
3. What potential intervention program could be developed based on the study's findings and the researchers' reflections to assist participants who works night shift?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Hugh Good (2023) identifies phenomenological qualitative research as a study in which the goal is to determine the way in which participants personally experience, comprehend, and cope with the life events related to the subject matter. This method prevents biases from the researcher, while making the interactions and real opinions of the participants central. As it focuses on people's reasons for doing things, their feelings, and attitudes, the current study intends to gain a rich understanding of how people and groups construct meanings for events in their lives.

Furthermore, Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) is also another method of data analysis that is qualitative in nature, and assists researchers to comprehend why participants say they managed to 'survive'. Interpersonal communication being the focus of 'participant-orientation' aspects allow IPA interviewees to narrate their 'lived-through' experiences as they please. This method centers on the phenomena in participants and allows them to justify concerning research outcomes as observed from the participant's perspective. The findings of the present work are consistent with the IPA style of research, and the current study uses a suitable paradigm for analysis.

Researchers used a phenomenological method to explore the lived experiences of night shift workers. It provides an understanding of their real-life experiences in specific conditions, like working during the night shift, and allows researchers to explore significant events in people's lives they, perhaps, have never faced.

Population and Sampling

The researchers applied purposive sampling in this qualitative research to explore the phenomenon of interest in depth. It is the perfect sampling technique for the study since it allows researchers to concentrate on specific individuals with the appropriate traits and experiences.

Purposive sampling technique applied by the researchers for the purpose of qualitative data from the participants of this research. According to Campbell et al. (2020), purposive sampling has been in existence for a long time back, and the opinions regarding the opinions whether it is simple or complex are neutral. Therefore, purposive sampling is used to ensure that the sample selected is in tandem with the study objectives which provide improved study reliability and credibility of the results. This study selected seven (7) night shift workers in Calamba, Laguna. As stated by Creswell and Poth (2018), phenomenological studies usually include a limited number of participants, usually between 5 and 25, to enable thorough exploration and thorough analysis of each person's experiences.

Additionally, Singh & Shareef (2024) mentioned that the primary criterion for determining sample size in qualitative research is data saturation. Saturation happens when more participants in a study do not produce new data or discoveries. At this point, the researcher might discontinue collecting data. Researchers must strike a balance between intended sample size and the number of volunteers needed to finish the study. Sample size is influenced by practical factors such as resource availability, planning limits, and participant access.

Participant of the Study

The study consisted of 7 participants, regardless of gender, who have been working night shifts for five years or more. The participants came from a range of professions, including international teachers, security guards, nurses, call center agents, and virtual assistants. This diversity guarantees that the participants have deep knowledge and experience with the demands and problems of night shift employment, which is required for the purposes of the study. Purposive sampling was used in the study to choose these participants. Purposive sampling is a non-probability sampling technique in which the researcher specifically selects subjects or groups according to specific traits or standards that correspond with the study question or goals (Crossman, 2020).

Research Instrument

The data has been created by researchers for the study with the help of research tool that was researcher-created semi-structured interview questions. The study instruments were the open-ended questions. This is how similar kind of question was going to be used by the researchers since it gave participants the opportunity to vocalize more and explain themselves for deeper and more comprehensive answers. Less structured questions in qualitative research interviewing allow participants to express concepts they already possess in their own views, providing a more diverse and extensive source of data. As identified by Creswell (2013), open-ended questions are more inclined to understand participants' views/feelings and the structure permits the identification of particulars and other unexpected information.

1. Hi, how are you today? (*Kumusta ka ngayon?*)
2. Can you tell us about your occupation? (*Maaari mo bang sabihin sa amin ang tungkol sa iyong trabaho?*)
3. How long have you been working on a night shift? (*Gaano katagal ka na nagtatrabaho sa night shift?*)
4. What made you stay? (*Bakit ka nagstay?*)
5. What made you decide to take up a night shift job? (*Ano ang nagtulak sa iyo na mag-apply sa isang night shift na trabaho?*)
6. Can you describe a typical night shift for you? (*Maaari mo bang ilarawan ang isang tipikal na night shift para sa iyo?*)

7. How does the work environment differ during the night compared to the day? *(Paano naiiba ang kapaligiran sa trabaho sa gabi kumpara sa araw?)*
8. What challenges do you face in transitioning from your night shift to daytime sleep? *(Anong mga hamon ang iyong kinakaharap sa paglipat mula sa iyong night shift hanggang sa pagtulog sa araw?)*
9. How do you manage your day sleep following night work? What affects day sleep in terms of quality and duration? *(Paano mo pinamamahalaan ang iyong pagtulog sa araw kasunod ng night work? Ano ang nakakaapekto sa pagtulog sa araw sa mga tuntunin ng kalidad at tagal?)*
10. How does working the night shift affect your mood and emotions? Have you experienced any changes in your mental health since starting night shifts? *(Paano nakakaapekto ang pagtrabaho sa night shifts sa iyong mood at emosyon? Nakaranas ka ba ng mga pagbabago sa iyong mental health mula noong simulan ang night shifts?)*
11. How does the company address the potential health and well-being concerns associated with night shift work? *(Paano tinutugunan ng kumpanya ang potensyal na mga alalahanin sa kalusugan at kagalingan na nauugnay sa night shift work?)*

Validation of the Instrument

In order to ensure construct validity and content validity, the study instrument was validated among the expert officials. The interview questions developed by the researchers and the research adviser required validation by three validators, who must be certificated psychologists or psychometricians. These qualitative measures were integrated into the instrument to finalize it and make it ready for distribution by adding expert recommendations and correlations.

Data Analysis

Following the gathering of data, all spoken and unspoken aspects, such as pauses, intonations, and emphasis, was transcribed into a written format. The transcripts were studied and reread several times by the researchers in order to familiarize themselves with the information and form their initial understanding of the phenomenon. The researchers made note of the thorough and in-depth conclusions drawn from the data after several readings. The notes were transformed by the researchers into themes that appear in the coded data. In addition, the next stage involved identifying similarities among the themes that surface, assigning a title to each cluster, and searching for connections among them. Ultimately, researchers composed the analysis and concisely convey the results, supported by quotations and illustrations drawn from the data.

Scope and Delimitations

This paper aimed specifically at identifying the lived experiences of night shift workers. The researchers conducted this study in a year of 2024, and the sampling technique to be used is purposive sampling, which targets specific samples as defined by

the researchers. There were seven participants recruited in Calamba, Laguna has been working for at least five years. Calamba is also an industrial hub for the CALABARZON area. The city has several industrial parks and business estates that provide accommodation for manufacturing and logistics-oriented businesses. Currently, Calamba is among the fastest-growing cities and is believed to keep growing for the coming years. In order to minimize possible errors and enhance the validity of the results, each of the selected participants was requested to answer the set of semi-structured open-ended interview questions developed by the researchers.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: How do night shift workers describe their personal experience during working?

Central Theme	Sub-Central Theme	Code	Description
1. Adapting to Work Demands	1.1 Adjusting to Shifts	Shift adjustment	Participants describe their ability to adapt to rotational or night shifts despite initial challenges.
	1.2 Embracing Night Shifts	Night shift preference	Participants express a preference for night shifts due to the manageable workload and quieter environment.
2. Valuing Workplace Rewards	2.1 Receiving Financial Benefits	Financial rewards	Competitive salaries and night differentials encourage participants to stay in their roles.
	2.2 Finding Fulfillment in Work	Workplace engagement	The dynamic nature of the job, opportunities for growth, and a sense of global interaction keep participants motivated.
3 Diverse Opinions			Participants have a different opinion

Thematic Chart A

The findings reveal that people remain at their place of work due to work accommodation or the importance they award to organizational incentives. The main theme of work demands still applies since the participants have to adapt to a complex schedule of working shifts and even some of them find it convenient to work during the night because they say it is less noisy and they don't get as many customers as during the day. Likewise, valuing workplace rewards is supported by the following participants stating that they enjoy financial gain by the end of the month or week from their high salaries, 'night differentials' among others, and most of all, the ability to feel appreciated by either employers or clients.

In the study by Lecca et al. (2021), the various difficulties through which the workers go through when working on shift rotation schedules have been well illustrated. The study shows the negative influences of shift work, including sleep deprivation and chronic health hazards, in connection with weaving of the circadian rhythm due to constantly shifting day and night shifts.

Also, Bonifacio's (2024) study pointing out that most workers feel they need to be financially rewarded for shifts worked during unsociable hours such as night shifts.

Research Question 2: What are the emerging themes based on the gathered data?

Figure 2. Emerging Themes

Figure 2 shows the emerging theme elaborates on the dimensions of Night Shift Work Experiences. **Health Challenges** range from emotional/mental health concerns such as stress and anxiety to physical and environmental factors, which may include lack of sleep or disturbances to the natural circadian rhythms of a person. **Work Demands** This refers to the need of employees to adjust to the peculiar demands of night shift, the factors that motivate them to choose this schedule, and the reasons some employees might prefer night shift jobs.

Also included in the framework is **Support Systems**, which incorporates all workplace initiatives to enhance the work environment and provide the night shift worker with some sources of support. **Coping Strategies** include how individuals cope with their difficulties, particularly in a workplace context, focusing on workplace flexibility and changes toward improving working through night shifts. The next is **Rewards**, being the value that workers assign to benefits including compensation and workplace incentives. This would include the last category called **Sleep Difficulties**. These have to do with difficulties regulating sleep patterns; a person who fails to sleep in the day and has, on average, poor-quality sleep overall. All of these categories provide an integrated view of how complex night shift work is.

Research Question 3: What potential intervention program could be developed based on the study’s findings and the researchers’ reflections to assist participants who works night shift?

AREA OF CONCERN	OBJECTIVES	STRATEGIES & ACTIVITIES	TIME FRAME	PERSONS INVOLVED	SOURCE OF FUND	SUCCESS INDICATORS
1. Sleep disturbances and fatigue	To improve sleep quality and reduce fatigue among night shift workers.	- Sleep hygiene workshops	Monthly	Occupational health specialists	Company funds	Workers report better sleep quality.
2. Work-life balance challenges	To help workers effectively manage time for personal and professional	- Time management and self-care training	Quarterly	- Family support initiatives	- HR representatives	- Flexible scheduling options

AREA OF CONCERN	OBJECTIVES	STRATEGIES & ACTIVITIES	TIME FRAME	PERSONS INVOLVED	SOURCE OF FUND	SUCCESS INDICATORS
	responsibilities.					
3. Mental health and stress management	To provide mental health support and stress relief strategies.	- Mindfulness and relaxation techniques	Bi-monthly	- Mental health professionals	Company & health insurance	Reduced stress-related absenteeism

JAP (Just and Positive) Intervention Program

JAP Intervention Program is a master workplace health program which is designed to improve the workers' well-being and work ability but this time for workers employed on the night shift. These three issues are the building blocks of the program: sleep disorder and tiredness, work-life conflict problems, and mental illness and stress control.

For sleep disturbance and somnolence, the program aims to improve the quality of sleep for night shift workers by conducting monthly sleep hygiene seminars. The occupational health professionals conduct the seminars with an aim to increase knowledge as it relates to regular sleeping habits like regular sleeping timetable, fewer electronic screens at night, and appropriate sleeping conditions. The company is sponsoring the program and is looking forward to self-reported quality of sleep improving, which will manifest in less tiredness and better work output. To cope with work-life balance, the program seeks to enable the workers to manage work time and private time more efficiently. This is done through regular time management and self-care workshops and family care programs to bolster systems that already exist for the workers. Human Resources members also play a role in offering flexible scheduling plans organized in sync with workers' personal timetables. All these are blended to enhance a better work-life balance, which means greater job satisfaction and reduced burnout. Lastly, the JAP Intervention Program is extremely centered on mental well-being and stress reduction. Bi-weekly relaxation and mindfulness training workshops are held for mental health management of employees. These are undertaken by mental health practitioners and complemented by a combination of health and corporate insurance funds. The success of this component is gauged in terms of reduced work-related stress absence, i.e., workers are better equipped to cope with work stress and remain emotionally robust.

In general, JAP Intervention Program is a valuable and equitable employee wellness policy on work-life assistance, mental well-being, and business culture wellbeing. With its well-defined aims and structured activities, the program not only advances employees' health but also works towards developing healthier and productive work culture.

DISCUSSION

1. In exploring the lived experiences of night-shift workers, central themes and their sub-themes suggested key strategies and successful adaptations that a night-shift worker can apply to function effectively. Several readings and detailed analyses of verbatim transcripts shaped vital insights into resilience and support systems integral to such experiences.
2. Outcomes of studies were categorized into 13 superordinate themes covering the lived experience of night workers with specific emphasis on coping and accommodation with their work environment. Meeting Needs at Work involved accommodation by the workers to work in rotation shifts within workplace and then in turn prefer to work at nights because of workload which may last sustainably and calm nature of working. Valuing Workplace Perks addressed the significance of pay and self-esteem to ongoing work. Selecting Evening Shifts emphasized the influence of scarce work opportunities and job offer accidents to optionality in deciding to make decisions in selecting the work shift. Working during the night also dominated as the better planned, better-organized workplace. In Coping with Night Shift, the respondents enumerated a list of tasks and concerns, from team management and normalizing to healthcare pressures and security issues. Sleep and Psychological and Social Problem Challenges explained night work as the etiology of emotional pain, insomnia, and loneliness. Workplace Support Systems were required, and well-being and health initiatives, economic benefits, were indicated by participants to help in facilitating accommodation. Coping Strategies for Night Shift involved engaging in activities of leisure and adaptive work policies support, which helped in maintaining mental functioning in addition to productivity at work. The themes collectively give a comprehensive overview of adaptive strategies and challenges of night shift workers.
3. Night shift workers need interventions that have critical modules on health-related issues, work demands, coping skills, rewards, and the presence of sleep-related problems. Health and wellness programs on psychological support, stress management, and sleep hygiene education was beneficial for workers on night shifts. Flexible shifts with job sharing and flexible options was needed to relieve some of the physical and psychological hardships of working the night shifts. The integral parts in creating a supportive work environment include provision of on-site amenities and empathetic management. Coping and resilience training would help workers manage stress, and fair compensation and rewards would motivate employees. Finally, sleep support programs with an improvement approach on

quality sleep and the control of circadian rhythms are essential for well-being. These interventions would improve worker health, satisfaction, and productivity.

Conclusions

1. Based on the study conducted and the results obtained, most of the participants expressed that they preferred night shift working since it enabled them to balance on both work and family responsibilities. Consequently, participants, and especially parents with children, opine that working during the night provides them with more time with their families, which they cherish despite possible social isolation and sleep loss. For instance, the participants illustrated how working a day shift would not enable them to be around in order to watch children after school or during other important family activities. Furthermore, night shifts give participants a chance to continue with other activities and work in other stations, improving their monetary position. Therefore, night shift work is convenient especially from the perspective of participants and their economic targets, though they have to compromise their sleep and social opportunities.
2. The study's other key finding is the critical role that workplace flexibility and support play in countering health and well-being challenges from shift work. Flexible scheduling like breaks or rest during a shift has been mentioned by employees and it helps in minimizing fatigue and lessens the side effect on the circadian rhythm. Not only that but having on site accommodations, like comfortable resting areas and food means that the working environment is more comfortable and that employees are in better physical and mental health. In addition, employers invest in health and wellness programs, like routine checkups and counseling for mental health, which will help in providing stress management and long-term good employee welfare. The companies support these measures that aim to improve the overall night shift experience and to reduce the risks from irregular work hours.
3. The study emphasizes that satisfying night shift a job is dependent upon adequate financial compensation and employee engagement. The necessity for an increase in night differentials was a given for workers even before there was any hazard pay, who, consistently, valued the measure of more reliable night differentials and more hazardous pay to indicate the risks and difficulties of night shifts. In addition, participants stressed the value of incentivizing via food and 'enrichment,' meaning night raffles, to boost morale and energy among crews. They are not only good for physical well-being, but it also creates a positive, supporting environment. Those companies that reward financially and engage their employees by recognizing the unique challenges of night shift work are more likely to enjoy higher retention, productivity and employee satisfaction. Several participants suggested more staff should be hired or shift hours shortened to lessen the load and pressure on night shift workers. Night shifts, due to understaffing, result in exhaustion, stress and workplace violence that negatively impact productivity and employee morale. It steps in if it is not properly staffed; if it has too many employees working there, and the workload becomes too much to handle, and there is much danger of burnout amongst the workers. Addressing staffing and workload issues will help companies

become more efficient, reduce employee stress and help create a more healthful work environment for night shift workers.

Recommendations

1. According to the results, employers should take initiatives to meet the specific needs and preferences of night shift workers. The flexible work arrangements, such as optional rotational or fixed night shifts, will allow employees to balance work with personal and familial responsibilities. Companies can fight sleep deprivation by providing sleep education programs, rest areas, or access to sleep aids to help workers stay healthier. Social programs such as team building and digital forums can help eliminate social isolation faced by night shift workers. The financial incentives of working night shifts make it mandatory for employers to provide higher differentials for night shifts and provide financial planning advice to ensure the workers maximize their pay effectively. Finally, routine health monitoring and surveillance of fatigue will promote the welfare of night workers so that the work done remains sustainable without adversely affecting their long-term health and quality of life. Such measures could make night shifts easier to endure and rewarding for employees.
2. To enhance the condition of work and performance of night shifts, employers may consider a solution that encompasses some of the considerations on workplace flexibility, financial reward, staffing and wellness programs at the workplace. Companies should use flexible scheduling as a policy while ensuring that on-site amenities to include comfortable places to rest in addition to ready-to-eat meals are extended to employees because these will give them a relatively healthy and sane life.
3. Competition-based financial incentives provided to employers should be bigger, showing greater night differentials and hazard pay, representing the unique challenges that go into night shift operations. Morale-boosting raffles and team events connect and encourage workers, which makes for a friendly work environment. Lastly, staffing shortages are alleviated by seeking additional workers or redistributing workloads. By integrating these measures, organizations can increase retention, improve productivity, and ensure the long-term welfare of their night shift workforce.
4. Future researchers should focus on how to best ameliorate work-life balance, monetary compensation, work burden, and mental wellness for those working the night shift. Research should explore how things like flexible scheduling, wellness programs and financial incentives, such as hazard pay, affect employee well-being and job satisfaction. However, staffed research, as opposed to research on how to schedule effectively to minimize burnout and optimize productivity, can also be highly beneficial. Examining the psychological consequences of night duty and considering industry specific challenges will yield targeted strategies and policies to ensure improved working conditions. By tackling these areas, policies can be developed to positively impact the overall well-being and efficiency of night shift workers.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

When conducting this research, it was crucial to prioritize considerations to ensure the well-being and rights of the participants. Before they take part, the researchers provided informed consent that clearly explains the purpose of the study, as well as any potential risks and benefits involved. maintain confidentiality and privacy at all times, respecting anonymity. Any information collected was treated with care for research purposes and stored securely. Participants had autonomy in their decisions. They were fully informed about their right to withdraw from the interview at any point if they feel uncomfortable or overwhelmed or wish to stop participating without facing any negative consequences.

Acknowledgments

This research would not have been possible without the support, guidance and efforts of many individuals. The researchers wish to express their deepest gratitude to the following:

Mr. Ian B. Pradilla, Adviser and respected lecturer of University of Perpetual Help System DALTA for his dedicated mentorship, insightful advice, and unwavering support, which greatly contributed to the successful completion of this work.

Ms. Charie Jane Lao, Mr. Bernardo Fernandez II, and Dr. Josephine Maningas PhD esteemed panelists, for their constructive feedback, expert knowledge and thoughtful suggestions that enhanced the quality of this research.

The Participants, for their willingness to take part in this study, without them, this research would not have been possible.

The Fourth Year Psychology Students of University of Perpetual Help System DALTA Calamba Campus, their classmates, for their encouragement, support and share moments of joy, which made the challenges of completing this undergraduate thesis more bearable.

Parents, for their endless love, guidance, understanding, patience, motivation, moral and financial support and believing in their ability to achieve this goal.

Most importantly, to the Almighty Father, for His blessing of life, wisdom, discernment, love, protection, and guidance that sustained them throughout this journey.

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